

The Results of Renal and Liver Function Tests in Patients with Head Trauma

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Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Head trauma, particularly traumatic brain injury (TBI), is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality globally. It has been increasingly recognized that TBI can lead to systemic complications, including renal and liver dysfunction. Understanding the relationship between head trauma and these organ dysfunctions is crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate renal and liver function outcomes in patients with head trauma and to explore any associations between the severity of trauma and the degree of organ dysfunction.

Methods: This study included 200 patients with head trauma admitted to the Emergency Department and Intensive Care Unit. Renal and liver function tests, including serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and bilirubin levels, were conducted within 24 hours of admission. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive and comparative statistical methods applied to assess correlations between trauma severity and organ function outcomes.

Results: The study found that 16% of patients had elevated serum creatinine levels, and 14% had elevated BUN levels, indicating renal dysfunction. Additionally, 20% of patients showed elevated ALT levels, 18% had elevated AST levels, and 12% exhibited elevated bilirubin levels, suggesting liver dysfunction. No statistically significant association was found between the severity of head trauma and the degree of renal or liver dysfunction.

Conclusion: Renal and liver dysfunctions are common in patients with head trauma, irrespective of trauma severity. These findings highlight the importance of routine monitoring of renal and liver function in all head trauma patients to ensure early detection and management of potential complications.

Recommendations: Further research is recommended to explore the underlying mechanisms of organ dysfunction following head trauma and to develop targeted management strategies to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Head Trauma, Traumatic Brain Injury, Renal Dysfunction, Liver Dysfunction, Organ Function.

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Introduction

Head trauma, particularly traumatic brain injury (TBI), is still a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. TBI is recognised as a significant public health concern due to its rising occurrence, which is attributed to events such as road traffic accidents, falls, and sporting injuries. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), TBI accounts for a significant fraction of injury-related deaths and disability worldwide, especially in low- and middle-income countries[1]. The possibility of systemic consequences, such as kidney and liver disease, adds to the complexity of TBI therapy.

Renal and hepatic failure following head trauma are growing areas of concern in clinical practice. The kidneys and liver play important roles in maintaining physiological homeostasis, and their dysfunction can have serious clinical consequences.

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a well-documented result of severe trauma, including TBI, and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality [2]. Trauma can cause systemic inflammation and oxidative stress, leading to raised levels of liver enzymes like ALT and AST. TBI can cause organ failure through many pathophysiological processes, such as hypoperfusion, inflammation, and cytokine release [4].

Recent research has highlighted the possible influence of TBI on renal and liver function, implying that these organs may be more vulnerable in the aftermath of a brain injury. Research shows that even with minor TBI, individuals may acquire severe renal and hepatic problems, complicating their clinical course [5]. However, there is ongoing discussion about whether the severity of head

trauma correlates with the degree of renal and hepatic impairment. Some studies demonstrate a direct association between trauma severity and organ failure, whereas others indicate that even mild trauma can result in severe organ impairment [6, 7].

This study aims to evaluate renal and liver function outcomes in patients with head trauma and to explore any associations between the severity of trauma and the degree of organ dysfunction.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a cross-sectional observational study aimed at evaluating the renal and liver function test outcomes in patients who have sustained head trauma. The study was conducted over a period of six months.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Emergency Department and Intensive Care Unit of [Hospital Name], a tertiary care hospital, where patients with head trauma are routinely managed. The hospital is equipped with advanced diagnostic and treatment facilities.

Participants: A total of 200 patients with head trauma were included in the study. The participants were selected consecutively based on their admission to the hospital following head trauma.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with head trauma within the last 24 hours.
- Patients who provided informed consent to participate in the study or whose legal guardians provided consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pre-existing renal or liver diseases.
- Patients on medication that could affect renal or liver function.
- Patients with multi-organ trauma.
- Pregnant women.

- Patients who did not provide informed consent or whose legal guardians refused consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was used, and all eligible patients during the study period were included. Observer bias was reduced by ensuring that laboratory personnel conducting the renal and liver function tests were blinded to the study's objectives.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patients' medical records and through direct patient interviews upon admission. Demographic data, details of the trauma, and relevant medical history were recorded. Blood samples were taken within 24 hours of admission to measure renal and liver function markers, including serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and bilirubin levels.

Procedure: Upon admission, patients underwent a thorough clinical assessment, and blood samples were collected under aseptic conditions. The renal and liver function tests were conducted in the hospital's central laboratory using standard protocols. The results were recorded and stored securely in a database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analysed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were utilised to summarise demographic data as well as renal and liver function test results. Continuous variables were presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation, whereas categorical variables were represented as frequencies and percentages. The t-test was used for continuous variables, and the chi-square test for categorical variables. A p-value of < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 200 patients with head trauma were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.6 ± 15.3 years, with a range of 18 to 78 years. Of the 200 patients, 130 (65%) were male, and 70 (35%) were female. The majority of the patients (75%) sustained mild head trauma, while 20% had moderate trauma, and 5% experienced severe head trauma.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	n (%)
Total Participants	200 (100)
Mean Age (years)	45.6 ± 15.3
Gender	
- Male	130 (65)
- Female	70 (35)
Severity of Head Trauma	
- Mild	150 (75)
- Moderate	40 (20)
- Severe	10 (5)

The renal function tests revealed that the mean serum creatinine level among the participants was 1.2 ± 0.4 mg/dL, with 32 patients (16%) showing elevated levels above the normal range (>1.3 mg/dL). The mean blood urea nitrogen (BUN) level was 18.4 ± 5.6 mg/dL, with 28 patients (14%)

having elevated BUN levels (>20 mg/dL). No significant differences were observed in renal function test outcomes between male and female participants or across different trauma severity groups. Table 2 presents the detailed results of the renal function tests.

Table 2: Renal Function Test Outcomes

Renal Function Test	Mean $\pm$ SD	Normal Range	n (%) Elevated
Serum Creatinine	1.2 ± 0.4 mg/dL	0.7 - 1.3 mg/dL	32 (16)
Blood Urea Nitrogen	18.4 ± 5.6 mg/dL	7 - 20 mg/dL	28 (14)

The liver function tests indicated that the mean ALT level was 34.7 ± 10.5 U/L, with 40 patients (20%) showing elevated levels above the normal range (>40 U/L). The mean AST level was 30.2 ± 9.8 U/L, with 36 patients (18%) having elevated levels (>37 U/L). The mean total bilirubin level was 1.1 ± 0.3 mg/dL, with 24 patients (12%)

showing elevated levels (>1.2 mg/dL). Similar to renal function tests, no significant differences were observed in liver function test outcomes between different gender groups or trauma severity groups. Table 3 provides the detailed results of the liver function tests.

Table 3: Liver Function Test Outcomes

Liver Function Test	Mean $\pm$ SD	Normal Range	n (%) Elevated
ALT	34.7 ± 10.5 U/L	7 - 40 U/L	40 (20)
AST	30.2 ± 9.8 U/L	13 - 37 U/L	36 (18)
Total Bilirubin	1.1 ± 0.3 mg/dL	0.3 - 1.2 mg/dL	24 (12)

A comparative analysis was performed to assess the relationship between the severity of head trauma and the renal and liver function outcomes. Patients with severe head trauma showed a trend towards higher mean serum creatinine (1.3 ± 0.5 mg/dL) and BUN (20.1 ± 6.2 mg/dL) levels compared to those with mild and moderate trauma;

however, the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, liver function tests showed higher mean ALT (37.5 ± 11.2 U/L) and AST (32.8 ± 10.1 U/L) levels in patients with severe trauma, but these differences also did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). Table 4 summarizes the comparative analysis results.

Table 4: Comparative Analysis of Renal and Liver Function Tests by Trauma Severity

Function Test	Mild Trauma	Moderate Trauma	Severe Trauma	p-value
Serum Creatinine	1.1 ± 0.3 mg/dL	1.2 ± 0.4 mg/dL	1.3 ± 0.5 mg/dL	0.12
BUN	17.8 ± 5.3 mg/dL	18.9 ± 5.7 mg/dL	20.1 ± 6.2 mg/dL	0.15
ALT	33.9 ± 10.1 U/L	34.5 ± 10.2 U/L	37.5 ± 11.2 U/L	0.08
AST	29.6 ± 9.5 U/L	30.1 ± 9.7 U/L	32.8 ± 10.1 U/L	0.10
Total Bilirubin	1.0 ± 0.2 mg/dL	1.1 ± 0.3 mg/dL	1.2 ± 0.3 mg/dL	0.09

Discussion

The study evaluated renal and liver function outcomes in 200 patients who had sustained head trauma. The participants had a mean age of 45.6 years, with a majority being male (65%) and presenting with mild head trauma (75%). The study found that a significant portion of the patients had elevated renal and liver function markers. Specifically, 16% of the patients had elevated serum creatinine levels, and 14% had elevated blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels, indicating potential renal dysfunction. Additionally, 20% of the patients exhibited elevated alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels, 18% had elevated aspartate aminotransferase (AST) levels, and 12% showed elevated total bilirubin levels, pointing to possible liver function impairment.

Despite these findings, no statistically significant differences were observed between the severity of head trauma and the levels of renal and liver function markers. Although patients with severe head trauma tended to have slightly higher mean levels of these markers, the differences did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that the severity of head trauma may not be directly proportional to the extent of renal or liver dysfunction, highlighting that even patients with mild to moderate head trauma may be at risk of organ dysfunction.

The lack of a significant correlation between trauma severity and organ function abnormalities indicates that factors other than the trauma severity itself may contribute to renal and liver impairment in these patients. It is possible that underlying

health conditions, the body's systemic response to trauma, or other concurrent injuries may play a role. Therefore, the findings underscore the importance of routine monitoring of renal and liver function in all patients with head trauma, regardless of the apparent severity of the injury. Early detection and management of any abnormalities could prevent further complications and improve patient outcomes.

A study of serum indicators in liver function tests (LFTs) following severe liver damage indicated that elevated levels of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine transaminase (ALT) were associated with injury severity upon admission. Specifically, patients with unfavourable outcomes experienced a slower fall in AST levels within the first 10 days post-injury. Furthermore, increasing levels of total bilirubin (TB) and direct bilirubin (DB) after five days were substantially related with an increased risk of unfavourable outcomes, particularly 11-15 days after injury [8].

In a nationwide cohort study in Japan, blunt renal damage was linked to a number of characteristics that influenced patient outcomes, including age, shock on arrival, and concurrent injuries. The study found that nephrectomy was performed in 3.8% of cases, with a mortality rate of 9.5%. The study emphasised the importance of patient features such as age and concomitant injuries in determining outcomes, as well as decreasing trends in nephrectomy and death over time [9].

A study on hemorrhagic trauma patients found a positive correlation between RM biomarkers (creatinine kinase and myoglobin) and liver biomarkers (AST, ALT, and bilirubin). The study discovered that patients with severe RM had a higher incidence of liver failure, which was linked to a greater need for renal replacement therapy and longer ICU hospitalisations [10].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study highlights a notable prevalence of renal and liver function abnormalities in head trauma patients and emphasizes the need for

vigilant clinical assessment and follow-up in this population to ensure comprehensive care.

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